

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BRUCE-PATTERSON****FIRST NAME: KERESE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Deleted: PROFESSOR DR KABIRU****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word for Mac Version 16.58

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1. Preparing a good academic paper (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 7-14)
2. Styles of writing (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 41-57)
3. American English versus British English (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 25-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 34-39)
5. Preparing a Response Paper (EUCLID 2021, 2-12)

Deleted: (samples below):**Commented [GK1]:** You omitted "e" after "n" in the spelling of Cleenwerck. Kindly correct this error across all citations.**Deleted: ¶****Formatted:** Numbered + Level: 1 + Numbering Style: 1, 2, 3, ... + Start at: 1 + Alignment: Left + Aligned at: 0.63 cm + Indent at: 1.27 cm

PREPARING A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

1) INTRODUCTION

My new academic journey, which began with excitement, quickly became daunting and overwhelming. I began questioning whether my knowledge, or clearly lack thereof, of essay writing, was sufficient to complete my Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.). Having read the Coursepack and viewing the associated videos, I am now convinced that my prior knowledge of essay writing and pronunciations was wholly insufficient. While familiarizing myself with the material, I found that I began revising my diction, use of words, and writing styles in my everyday communication and preparing legal opinions at work. It is evident that I have some relearning and learning to be done.

In my response paper 1, I will focus on the five (5) areas that stood out to me in completing the material: preparing a good academic paper, styles of writing, the difference between American and British English, plagiarism, and preparing a Response Paper. These key areas are what I seek to master as I evolve my writing skill throughout my DILT programme and beyond.

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The introduction to the material and the DILT programme led me to phrases I was never familiar with. The use of 'formal prose' was one such term. After exhausting the material, I learned that it was another reference to academic writing. I began using the term

interchangeably in my revision notes to familiarize myself with the phrase. As I embark on this journey of repeated preparation of academic papers, one thing I will gather from my perusal of the documents, formal prose is void of personal opinion and, as such, is objective and fact-based. In contrast, my Response Papers are personal and present my views and understanding of the material. I begin my journey of mastering the difference.

2) PREPARING A GOOD ACADEMIC PAPER

Academic writings are nonfictional work aimed at communicating an answer to a hypothesis and the author's idea based on evidence researched (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 7). I found myself employing the methods described in starting an essay in preparing this paper. I jotted my notes, defined my question, developed my plan, researched unfamiliar terms, and then executed my attempt at writing a good academic paper (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 7). The Coursepack provided was sufficient in assisting me in understanding that I truly need to master the art of preparing a good paper and being mindful of punctuations, spelling differences, and the proper use and meanings of Latin Abbreviations and Expressions by following the requisite steps.

I completed the material thinking that all the material needed to be concise and summarized in this Response Paper, but I then reviewed *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui: Euclid University, where I was informed that I should focus on at least five (5) key concepts of the material studied and my reaction to the material. As such, I began organizing my ideas and came to realize I had to select the key information I wanted to use to provide the answer to my question: How does one prepare an excellent academic paper? The answer rests with the aforementioned steps and zoning in on the research.

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Research is critical to any academic paper and will form the bulk of the evidence used to argue a hypothesis. It is critical to determine what I already know about the topic, what I need to know to write the paper, what material is useful to my topic, and will the material support my answer (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 8). These are essential in organizing my ideas, structuring my paper, and then writing the paper. Of course, with research comes referencing, a critical aspect of the paper that not only substantiates my answer in my paper, but it also rubbishes the notion of plagiarism.

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The wealth of information gathered from research can be daunting in preparing a paper. It is advised that I remain focused on my topic, critically assess the information, deduce what must be used to answer my question, and then write clearly (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 13). I learned to also employ a two-prong approach in thinking while executing my writing: employ creative thinking and to employ critical thinking. Creative thinking will encourage me to broaden my ideas and scope, while critical thinking will narrow my focus and ideas (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 19). The two will allow for a balanced essay where facts aligning with ideas are presented along with others that differ, giving a comprehensive understanding of the topic.

It is evident that I ought to communicate my ideas based on the evidence considering that writing styles matter more than I dare to know.

3) STYLES OF WRITING

On registration, EUCLID University presented me with a link to Turabian (Chicago Style) rules of referencing. The need to establish what form of English the student would employ was also at the fore. This will be elaborated on in my next point. Both the aforementioned are critical to what style is acceptable and recommended within the University and what I ought to practice going forward.

Style guides, which are generally associated with types of writing, allow for consistency (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 41). I recall the Coursepack citing examples of the style guides of the British Broadcasting Commission (BBC) website and the evidence of the preferred style being published for Contributing Writers usage. This example allowed me to understand the point that the style of writing negates personal style and allows for a piece of writing to be consistent with the publication (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

I also learned that styles are not only limited to punctuation and correct grammar. There are varying aspects that are paramount to a style employed; these include but are not limited to: font usage, preferred sentence lengths, accepted terminology, structure, and referencing (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 41). A style guide is a critical tool for any writer. I found that I began familiarizing myself with the Turabian style through the disclosed link and practicing my referencing and style guide in my writing of opinions in my professional capacity. I must admit, I have not mastered this yet and intend to do so as I continue my studies. Perusing the material in Period 2, I find that I have much more to learn.

Citations and referencing are critical in the preferred style of writing. The method and citing references are essential to practice and master, as I have seen in Professor Dr Gulma's *Basic ACA-401 Tutorial* video presentation. This comes as a challenge to me having practiced, for some time, the use of the American Psychological Association (APA) style of documenting sources in my Undergraduate Degree papers. In preparation for Bar Examinations, the mode of case, journal, and legislation citations differed. I observed similarities with both styles (APA and Turabian), especially concerning in-text referencing. The difference is seen in the use of footnotes. While this is allowed in Turabian (not necessarily for Response Papers), it is not in APA.

Citing an author's work may also include lifting a sentence or more (with referencing, of course). The use of quotations or indexed paragraphs is essential, depending on the length of the quotation. I have learned that the writing style dictates the appropriate length of sentences to include in a paragraph or to have it stand by itself. I have also learned the appropriate punctuation (dashes and ellipses) to use in given circumstances.

Proper punctuation, Cleenwerck & Gulma (2021, 16) and Latin abbreviations are also instrumental in styles. They are even more so depending on the type of English a writer employs. I was born and raised in Jamaica. We 'use' British (broken) English. However, by approximation and globalization, the United States (U.S.) version of English has been employed more than we care to admit. As such, the two are used interchangeably used

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without much recognition and correction. I, however, will not make that mistake in preparing my papers for the University and will only employ British English with the Chicago style of writing.

4) UNITED STATES ENGLISH V BRITISH ENGLISH

Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE), as they are referred to, are confused in my country. Especially with the evolution and predominance of social media, the SAE is predominantly pushed on the younger generation, who now fail to recognize the difference. The popularity of the SAE is also a result of the prevalence of the publishing industry in the U.S., its wealth compared to the United Kingdom's (U.K.) influences, and several other factors (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 25).

I was reminded of the different pronunciations and spelling of words, the additional or different meanings of the words and nouns, and the general use of the collective nouns 'has' versus 'have' (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 26). I now know that I will undoubtedly have to remind myself and relearn the SBE for consistency in my papers.

5) PLAGIARISM

The Collins Dictionary and Thesaurus define plagiarism as stealing ideas or passages from another's work and presenting them as one's own. The Coursepack defines plagiarism similarly. This illustrates, to me, that there can be no confusion as to what plagiarism is. It cannot be emphasized enough how grave an offense it is. I reiterate and note from the repeated reminders that citing and referencing are extremely important to writing papers.

The Coursepack also assisted me in determining what is helpful to cite and what may not be necessary to cite but will not be considered plagiarism. One such example is information deemed general knowledge and a well-known fact (Cleenwerck & Gulma 2021, 37).

I am reminded that it is immaterial where the information used was derived from. Turabian gives the option to cite a reference from a book to audio-visual content and even personal communication. "Turabian A Manual for Writers," The Chicago Manual of Style accessed September 9, 2022. The stark importance of all that I have learned is that referencing is critical to avoid plagiarism.

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6) PREPARING A RESPONSE PAPER

Professors Cleenewerck and Gulma were careful to outline the 'dos' and 'don'ts' of writing a response paper. I note in the material provided that they were careful to outline the different headings a Response Paper (RP) should have, how critical it is to stick with

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the template formatting provided, and the proper format in saving and sending one's response papers for their respective periods (EUCLID 2021, 2).

I must admit that I have drafted this Response Paper three (3) times. I told myself that practice becomes perfect, and I will improve as I continue my studies and master my writing skills. In my numerous drafts of this RP, I am now more comfortable with the format and allowing myself to be broken into the habit of utilizing this template. The points in the document will be kept close and used as a constant reminder that the summary of the material should be kept objective and factual and that I am to maintain a personal understanding throughout my paper.

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7) CONCLUSION

The daunting introduction to my doctoral programme was sufficient to understand the wealth of information I have to consider and what I will need to practice to process and document it. I have no doubt that the several drafts of this paper and the length of time employed to complete the first Period have allowed me to now be baptized in my new endeavour. I now know what is expected of me and the time and effort I will have to commit to completing my academic journey through immaculate academic writing.

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The coursepack and related information was indeed the start I needed to condition my mind to complete my Ph.D. in International Law and Treaty Law. I shall use ACA-401D coursepack as my point of reference throughout my studies.

REFERENCES

Collins Dictionary and Thesaurus. 2011. Fifth Edition. Glasgow: HarperCollins Publishers

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Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.